

Family Health Promotion

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Discussion Board

Define family member roles; deliberate the importance of family roles and the responsibilities of family members on health promotion

Health promotion is a concept that was introduced at an international conference organized by the World Health Organization in Ottawa, Canada in January 1986. The representatives at the conference drafted a joint charter on health promotion. The family health promotion ideals were emphasised in this report. The report emphasized that individuals are responsible for their own health, while all sectors of society have a responsibility to facilitate the development of good health. The overall objectives are more healthy life years in the population and to reduce inequalities in health between socioeconomic groups, ethnic groups and gender. It is suggested as an ideal that certain knowledge should be the basis for both policy and practice in health promotion. Measures planned and implemented, should as far as possible be based on knowledge of causes and effects (Davis et.al, 2003).

The message priority measures directed against lifestyle diseases (cardiovascular disease, cancer, type 2 diabetes etc.) and mental disorders, especially depression. Healthy lifestyle choices have prominently, and children and young people a priority. Physical inactivity, unhealthy eating habits, use of tobacco and other drugs comprise the major priority (Hanson et.al, 2005).

Family health promotion models such as Role-performance model, Adaptive model and Eudemonistic model emphasizes strategies for preventing both physical and mental health problems and disorders and promote family health. The message focuses on the key challenges when it comes to getting an overall effort to improve child and adolescent mental health; as well as that of parents and other family members. It emphasizes strategies that focus on the environment, family, school, recreational and support system puts children and young people's own resources and coping ability in the center (Davis et.al, 2003).

In line with this, the main strategies in family health promotion to be:

- Build a health policy
- Creating supportive environments for health and development
- Strengthen the community's opportunities for control over their own future
- Develop personal skills that puts people able to make choices that promote health
- Reorient health services towards preventative health (Hanson et.al, 2005).

Within the five main areas of psychology can play a significant role, both in terms of contributions from research and practice, particularly in relation to how to create supportive environments and develop personal skills? These issues are central to positive psychology and family health promotion is an important area of positive psychologists (PSI, 2004).

References

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